

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D9.2

Impact assessment report

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Contents

1. INTRODUCTION.....	7
1.1 Purpose of the document.....	7
1.2 Scope of the document.....	7
1.3 Structure of the document.....	7
2. PILOTING PROJECT BUSINESS PROJECTION.....	8
3. PILOTING IMPACT ASSESMENT.....	11
3.1 SoEL IMPACT ASSESSMENT IDENTIFICATION.....	11
3.1.1 Questions related to project management.....	13
3.1.2 Questions related to technical aspects	18
3.2 SoEL IMPACT ASSESSMENT ANALYSIS	24
3.3 SoEL IMPACT ASSESSMENT EVALUATION AND TREATMENT.....	26
4. CONCLUSIONS.....	30
5. REFERENCES.....	31
Annex I: Participant Information Sheet Template.....	33
Annex II: Informed consent form Template.....	36

List of Figures

Figure 1. Impact Assessment Methodology	11
Figure 2. Example Privacy Term.....	15
Figure 3. Invitation email to the “European Robotic & AI projects applied to inspection and maintenance” PILOTING workshops.	16
Figure 4. Description of the WP1 deliverables required in the Post-Grant Requirement document.	17

List of Tables

Table 1. Acronyms list	6
Table 2. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Refinery Impact Scenario.....	9
Table 3. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Bridge/Viaduct Impact Scenario.	10
Table 4. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Tunnel Impact Scenario.	10
Table 3. List of PILOTING partners who have participated in the SoEL Impact Assessment Identification questionnaires.....	13
Table 4. Identification of each consortium partner has participated in each questionnaire.	13
Table 5. Risk matrix	25
Table 6. Management identified risks	26
Table 7. Technical identified risks	27

Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AESA	Agencia Estatal de Seguridad Aérea (“Spanish Agency for Aerial Safety”)
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DMS	Data Management System
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
F2F	Face to face
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IA	Impact Assessment
I&M	Inspection and maintenance
IVP	Intelligent and Visualization Portal
MTOW	Maximum Take-Off Weight
SoEL	Social, Ethical and Legal
SoTA	Safe and secure over-the-air
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
WP	Work Package

Table 1. Acronyms list

1. INTRODUCTION

Given that PILOTING is a European Union (EU) funded project, it must respect the principles of the EU legal framework. Then, it is necessary to ensure that PILOTING, both as a project and a future commercial product based on PILOTING technologies, complies with the European data protection framework as well as other legal and ethical obligations. Work Package 9 aims to ensure compliance through conducting an impact assessment (IA) against the SoEL requirements, which was the subject matter of deliverable D9.1. The role of this deliverable within that context is to provide a detailed report on this impact assessment carried out by FERROVIAL in cooperation with the consortium.

1.1 Purpose of the document

The primary aim of the PILOTING impact assessment report will be to assess the potential impacts of applying the PILOTING project in terms of adherence to the social, ethical and legal principles outlined in Deliverable 9.1 – ‘Principles for impact assessment of PILOTING against SoEL requirements’. As described in Deliverable 9.1, the PILOTING project may result in a risk to privacy, to the right to the protection of personal data, as well as pose challenges to the existing regulation of unmanned vehicles or novel technologies as artificial intelligence (AI) covered by PILOTING. For this reason, in the D9.1, specific guidelines, which define all applicable SoEL requirements against which the impact assessment must be performed, have been elaborated. Therefore, this deliverable will focus on the methodology of the assessment regarding to data protection, privacy, ethical and liability aspects in the PILOTING project.

1.2 Scope of the document

This document (D9.2) represents the first step in terms of an assessment of whether the principles, key criteria and frameworks described within D9.1 will be adhered to by the PILOTING project, integration the results of the different impact assessment and including also recommendations on how to improve PILOTING developments in these topics.

1.3 Structure of the document

The Impact assessment report has the following sections:

- Section 1 describes the purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable.
- Section 2 makes an overview of the PILOTING project business projection, in order to analyse which applicable SoEL requirements must be prioritised within the PILOTING Impact assessment to facilitate the long-term exploitation of the project results.
- Section 3 details the approach of the PILOTING project consortium to the SoEL Impact assessment and how the possible risk of non-compliance with the SoEL requirements will be: 1) identified using questionnaires; 2) analysed, and 3) evaluated and treated in order to avoid or minimise the possible negative consequences and impacts.
- Section 4 presents the conclusions of this deliverable.

2. PILOTING PROJECT BUSINESS PROJECTION

The aim of this report is to ensure that any element of PILOTING and its foreseen applications are in line with the SoEL requirements. This approach will allow designing a tailored strategy that balances the needs of all the stakeholders involved and the legal requirements and ethical principles at each step of the project, through the specifications' definition to the technical developments and pilot demonstrations. These actions have been taken in order to ensure that the development of the project, in a socially, ethically and legally acceptable way, is facilitated in order to promote its long term exploitation.

As was defined in the deliverable D9.1, the impact of the SoEL applicable principles have been analysed, considering each PILOTING Uses Cases (six "PILOTING Impact Scenarios" have been defined related to the applicable requirements). Then, within the PILOTING Impact Assessment, the business projections of these will be taken into account.

As was described in the proposal, there are three main challenges in the industry concerning the I&M process: 1) Reduce or avoid inspectors in hazardous locations; 2) Increase the quality of the data obtained during inspections and 3) Reduce the cost of inspection activities, which can be improved with the PILOTING system. The business projection for each "PILOTING Impact Scenario" is analysed below.

➤ **Refineries "PILOTING Impact Scenarios"**

In refineries, the inspection activities are traditionally executed by personnel that require access to specific locations. Up to 90% of these activities are carried out by working at elevated locations with the use of ladders, scaffold, rope accesses or cranes, and sometimes in the presence of high temperatures or toxic materials. Normally, associated costs due to the use of access devices, is many orders of magnitude larger than the measurement cost by itself. For example, it is estimated that around 80% of the budget for ultrasonic thickness measurements (which supposes about 60% to 75% of the inspection cost in this type of facility) is devoted to the infrastructure for safe access of the inspectors. The needed measurements for a standard size refinery (processing 100.000 barrels per day) can be estimated at 50.000.

The use of robots, especially aerial robots and crawlers, as the solutions developed in PILOTING, opens a new door for difficult access inspections. Also, the use of ground robots is very useful for monitoring activities in isolated refineries or dangerous areas.

As an example of estimating the potential market for these new solutions, in the case of use of aerial robots for difficult access inspections, we believe that the PILOTING system will be another tool available to inspectors, and that it will coexist with other traditional systems such as scaffolding or rope access, so that not all inspectors will use it all the time. Due to the usage of the PILOTING system, it can be estimated that 50% of the inspections will not necessitate any infrastructure. For the current example (measurements by human inspectors only), assume 30% simple access and 70% difficult access, with a 50% inspector measurement efficiency (to account for time for reporting, shift overhead, and the avoidance of excessively long measurement tasks that could compromise safety,

etc.), inspection expenditures for 50 000 points over three years are estimated to be over 3 million euros. 101 refineries are located in Europe, which means a potential market of more than 300M€/year.

To access this market, at least in Europe, will be essential to develop final solutions (once these are implemented in the market) that comply with the SoEL requirements defined in the Guidelines for the impact assessment in the deliverable D9.1 (see Table 2).

Impact Scenarios	Social	Ethical	Legal
Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	UAV regulation
Impact Scenario 2: Refinery - Crawler	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	-
Impact Scenario 3: Refinery- UGV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	-

Table 2. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Refinery Impact Scenario.

➤ **Bridges/Viaducts “PILOTING Impact Scenarios”**

In terms of the bridges and viaducts, most of these civil/transport infrastructures have been in use for more than half a century. Then, these are degrading due to aging, environmental conditions, increased loading, change in usage, damages caused by human/natural elements, inadequate maintenance, and deferred repairs, and new strategies for inspection, assessment, and repair work are urgently required.

In the EU's principal networks of transnational, primary, and secondary highways, there are more than a million bridges/viaducts [1] and more than 500.000 rail bridges. In reality, 330.000 rail bridges (or 66 percent) are over 50 years old, and almost 60% of road or rail bridges (or 840.000 bridges) are composed of concrete [2].

Visual inspection is one of the most common and significant inspection processes on bridges and viaducts. This examination is usually carried out by an operator who must work at height, and is used to discover potential infrastructure defects (such as cracks, corrosion, delamination, water leakage, etc.).

PILOTING solution proposes to perform the inspection with an aerial robot-based solution that will be able to acquire high resolution images of the bridge/viaduct that afterwards will be analysed by artificial intelligence-based software.

From Europe's 1.5 million bridges, around 55.000 require continuous inspection due to their criticality or age. Assuming 1/3 can be inspected with robotics technologies, then the potential market of the PILOTING solution in the bridge/viaduct market is around 70M€/year.

To ensure that the PILOTING system will subsequently be exploitable, and will be able to access this potential market, we need to ensure during all phases of the design and development of the solution that the SoEL requirements are met, which in this PILOTING Scenario are:

Impact Scenarios			Social	Ethical	Legal
Impact Scenario 4: Bridge/Viaduct- UAV			GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	UAV regulation

Table 3. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Bridge/Viaduct Impact Scenario.

➤ Tunnels “PILOTING Impact Scenarios”

One of the primary issues in tunnel inspection is the development of a system that allows for a full inspection of the tunnels while limiting the shutting time in order to reduce traffic effect. This system should be able to inspect the tunnel's structural elements (looking for cracks, spalling, delamination, calcium/water leakages, and so on). PILOTING proposes a revolutionary combined ground-aerial system that allows optimising this process.

In terms of the tunnels market, the total length of operational transportation tunnels in Europe exceeds 15,000 kilometers [3], of which more than half are over 30 years old, 38% are in the south and vulnerable to earthquakes, and all are vulnerable to car accidents, explosions, and material deterioration. According to studies conducted by the French Ministry of Transport, basic tunnels require an average of 3 permanent technicians per kilometer for inspection (besides the intervention teams). For complex bi-directional tunnels in the Alps, this number can reach up to 6-9 technicians (cross-border tunnels with heavy traffic). This is equivalent to a salary of 200K Euros per km/year and only includes salaries [4]. Particularly for the PILOTING use case, Metsovo tunnel, this means around 270K€ just in salaries plus all the required equipment to perform the inspections.

Since there are 15.000 km of tunnels in Europe, and 50% are more than 30 years old, and assuming 1/4 can be inspected with robotics technologies, then the potential market of the PILOTING solution in the Tunnel Scenario, just in Europe, is around 170M€/year .

To ensure that the PILOTING system is later exploitable and can access this prospective market, PILOTING consortium will ensure that the solution meets all the applicable SoEL requirements:

Impact Scenarios	Social	Ethical	Legal
Impact Scenario 5: Tunnel- UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	-
Impact Scenario 6: Tunnel – UGV	GDPR	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	-

Table 4. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Tunnel Impact Scenario.

Although, the target market is being taken into account throughout the whole PILOTING system design process, at this early stage of the project, this first version of the deliverable is more focused on the technologies developed within the project. In the next report, deliverable D9.4, the impact assessment will also take into account the business projections (once more experience has been gained and it will be easier to identify value propositions for the end-users and select the most interesting potential business cases).

3. PILOTING IMPACT ASSESMENT

As was defined in the D9.1, the impact assessment methodology to be followed within the project has three steps (see Figure 1):

1. Impact assessment Identification: to help the identification of possible risks related with non-compliance with SoEL requirements. To perform this assessment, PILOTING consortium will employ questionnaires.
2. Impact assessment analysis: the quantification and qualification will be performed during the analysis of the identified risks.
3. Impact assessment evaluation and treatment: A contingency plan will be defined to avoid/minimise each identified risk.

Figure 1. Impact Assessment Methodology

3.1 SoEL IMPACT ASSESSMENT IDENTIFICATION

This section details the approach of the PILOTING project consortium to the SoEL Impact assessment. This impact assessment identification has been based on the answer to a number of questionnaires.

In this first stage of the project, the questionnaires have been distributed among the PILOTING partners. Since the project involves all the actors that conform the full value chain of the I&M sector, including: high-profile research and innovation partners, world-leading technological companies, highly specialised SMEs, inspection and maintenance service providers, and companies that operate or own infrastructure in both the oil and gas and civil infrastructure/transport sectors, we believe that the answers collected of the project partners could generate a complete view for the SoEL impact assessment identification. In addition, the PILOTING consortium includes partners with extensive knowledge of the unmanned aerial robot regulation. In fact, CATEC, the project coordinator, has an active role in the definition of future industrial standards for aerial robots, being a member of the WG-105 at EUROCAE (European aeronautical standardization body). This working group (WG.105) is the one at EUROCAE specialized on UAS. Also, CATEC is a member of UNE's UAS working group which is the Spanish representative for ISO committees. Then, within the project exists an excellent ecosystem for analysing the potential impact of non-compliance with any SoEL requirements.

In the next iteration of this deliverable, D9.4, it is planned to address the questionnaires to a wider audience, also involving external stakeholders and members of the I&M industry. The result of this new version will be an updated list of risks, once the PILOTING solution is further developed, with feedback from external actors related to the project developments: public institutions, scientific/research communities, standardization entities, regulatory authorities as well as other potential end-users.

The questionnaires have been structured in two main areas:

- Requirements related to project management in PILOTING project, in relation to personal data protection, ethical principles and privacy.
- Requirements related to technical aspects of PILOTING project, in relation to the risk that may arise due to the use of unmanned vehicles and novel technologies as artificial intelligence in the framework of the project and future products.

The questions included in these questionnaires have been chosen by PILOTING consortium, in order to ensure compliance with all the applicable SoEL requirements, defined in the Guidelines for the impact assessment (see deliverable D9.1).

Table 5 shows which PILOTING partners have participated in answering the questionnaires.

PILOTING partner	Contact	Email
CATEC	Antidio Viguria Jiménez	aviguria@catec.aero
ETHZ	César Cadena	cesarc@ethz.ch
USE	Anibal Ollero	aollero@us.es
CHEVRON	Russell Brown	russell.brown@chevron.com
FERROVIAL	David Delgado	david.delgado@ferrovial.com
WTR	Remy Schmid	remy.schmid@inspection-robotics.com
APPLUS	Bart Hartge	bart.hartge@applusrvis.com

EGNATIA	Panagiotis Panetsos	PPANE@egnatia.gr
QUASSET	Luc Stakenborg	luc.stakenborg@quasset.com
	Arnaud Andrianavalomahefa	arnaud.andrianavalomahefa@quasset.com
SINTEF	Asbjørn Berge	asbjorn.berge@sintef.no
INLECOM	Thomas Krousarlis	thomas.krousarlis@inlecomsystems.com
ICCS	Kostas Bouklas	kostas.bouklas@iccs.gr
RBNK	Miquel Cantero	mcantero@robotnik.es

Table 5. List of PILOTING partners who have participated in the SoEL Impact Assessment Identification questionnaires.

The questionnaires related to project management have been mainly answered by CATEC, as project coordinator, with the valuable comments from the rest of the consortium, whereas the questionnaires related to the project technical development has been answered by all the involved technical partners. In this document, the PILOTING consortium responses are presented as a summary of the main conclusions drawn from each individual partner, in order not to be repetitive.

Questionary	PILOTING partner contribution
Questions related to the project management	
Questions related to data protection	All partners
Questions related to the technical aspect	
Questions related to data protection	All partners
Question related to the operation of Unmanned Vehicles	Robotic solutions developers (CATEC, ETHZ, USE, WTR, SINTEF, RBNK)
Question related to ethical and legal aspects related to Artificial Intelligence	Artificial intelligence (ICCS, USE, INLECOM)

Table 6. Identification of each consortium partner has participated in each questionnaire.

3.1.1 Questions related to project management

3.1.1.1 Questions related to data protection

1. What types of data will be collected? Can a natural person be identified with the collected data (in itself or by combination with other data)?

In the context of PILOTING management, activities like surveys or workshops, that involve the collection and processing of personal data, will be carried out. The type of information that can be collected during these activities includes name, surname, email, entity or work position. This data will be collected only for the project and will be confidential and accessible only by authorised personnel.

2. Will you collect any personal data during the project activities? If so, please describe.

As mentioned above, personal data as name, surname, email, entity or work position will be collected in some project activities to identify the feedback from the I&M community.

3. How do you plan to collect the views and feedbacks of stakeholders?

In the context of PILOTING project, different ways has been defined to obtain feedback from the stakeholders:

1. Coordination with other inspection-related projects (such as RIMA DIH or ATLANTIS) has been promoted.
2. A PILOTING User Group has been defined in order to disseminate and obtain feedback of the project results from a wide group of stakeholders.
3. Organisation of workshops and strong participation to related events in the field of I&M community.
4. A PILOTING profile has been created in [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#).

4. If you process personal data, do you handle special categories of personal data (sensitive data)?

The overall goal is to minimise the collection of sensitive personal data as much as possible. However, when not possible, such data will be collected only for the project and will be preserved for 48 months (PILOTING duration).

5. If personal data are processed, does the collected data meet the requirements of relevancy and accuracy? How do you ensure that data will remain accurate when disclosing it to third parties?

If we processed personal data, these will remain secure and will be accessible at any time only by persons with special permission upon request. Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties. Nevertheless, if a third party request any information, the involved party will be appropriately informed in advance.

6. If personal data are processed, can you estimate the amount of processed data and the number of data subjects?

Yes. In the context of PILOTING project, it is planned to collect personal data mainly through:

- Organisation of a PILOTING User Group to obtain feedback from a large set of external entities and stakeholders from the I&M community. Nevertheless, in the PILOTING invitation email, a specific clause of accomplishing GDPR requirements is included. At the time of writing this deliverable, there are 205 members registered in the PILOTING User Group. During PILOTING project, we believe that the order of magnitude will be maintained.

In addition, people from outside PILOTING User Group and PILOTING consortium could be invited to the workshops or demonstration sessions organised within the project. Personal data will be treated under GDPR requirements because in the Event registration process or Attendance sheet (to be signed) a specific clause of accomplishing GDPR requirements will be included.

➤ **Question related to data controller**

7. If personal data are processed, how will be managed by PILOTING consortium?

The GDPR requirements will be accomplished during project's life cycle. All PILOTING partners are aware of the importance of fulfillment GDPR regulation as it is described in deliverable 9.1 "Principles for impact assessment of PILOTING against SoEL requirements" and 1.2 "POPD Requirement N°2".

Finally, PILOTING project consortium has appointed to Inmaculada Huertas Olivares, from CATEC, as Data Protection Officer.

8. Would an organisational change (whether in a consortium or in a single organisation) affect the processing of personal data in any way?

No, all PILOTING partners will follow the guidelines agreed for the processing of personal data (see deliverable D1.2 and D9.1). In case of an organisational change, all partners are committed not to disseminate project information to the No-disclosure of information clause of the Grant Agreement.

9. Will any personal data be transferred to third countries? If so, does the third country provide adequate protection? What is the legal basis of the transfer?

There is no intention of transferring personal data to third countries.

10. How is compliance with the data protection law demonstrated?

Following the applicable legislation, the data subjects will be informed (Art. 12,13/GDPR) before/at the point of activity through different options:

- a) Sending the Participant Information Sheet (see Annex I: Participant Information Sheet Template) and after that the people involved will sign an Informed consent form (see Annex II: Informed consent form Template) before undertaking data collection activities.
- b) Submitting privacy terms that must be select within web forms. In addition, the objectives of the activity shall be communicated and available. As example see Figure 2

Complete your registration ×

Email* First name*

Last name* Avatar

I agree to [Livestorm's Terms of Service](#) and the use of personal data as explained in [Livestorm's Privacy Policy](#). * ⓘ

Figure 2. Example Privacy Term

Until now, it has not been possible to hold F2F events with members outside the consortium (in fact the only F2F meeting so far has been the KOM in January 2020) due to the health restrictions imposed by the covid-19 pandemic. Then, concerning the options described:

- a) The Participant Information Sheet and Informed consent form are addressed to F2F events so, during this period, these have not been distributed/completed. Once the F2F events start, concrete completed examples will be included in the next version of this deliverable (D9.4), as annexes.
- b) The option chosen during this period has been the option b, submitting privacy terms in the web forms. As mentioned above, all the external participants in project activities have been dully informed of the purpose of the activity in which they are participating and how their data will be treated (a privacy note has been included in the invitation emails). As example, Figure 3 shows once of the invitations send trough the PILOTING User Group mailing list to the “European Robotic & AI projects applied to inspection and maintenance” PILOTING workshop.

Dear PILOTING User Group member,

I would like to invite you to an online workshop as part of PILOTING project activities (<https://pilotng-project.eu/>).

This Workshop will be oriented to present an overview of all active European Robotics & AI projects that apply Robotics and AI technologies to Inspection and Maintenance activities of any sector or application.

Then, it is a great opportunity to catch, in a single day, the leading innovative robotic technologies that are being developed for I&M industry.

The following projects will be presented: PILOTING (<https://pilotng-project.eu/>), RIMA (<https://rimanetwork.eu/>), AERIAL-CORE (<https://aerial-core.eu/>), METRICS (<https://metricsproject.eu/>) and OMICRON, among others pending confirmation.

You can register to the Workshop using the following link: <https://www.eventbrite.es/e/european-robotics-ai-workshop-applied-to-inspection-and-maintenance-tickets-157605647735^>

*Workshop connection details will be sent by email previously to the workshop date.
 **Workshop co-organized by the euRobotics Aerial Robotics and RIMA H2020 Project (through the Inspection and Maintenance, and Aerial Robotics Topic Groups).

Best regards, Antidio Viguria (PILOTING Project Coordinator).

You are receiving this email since you have been included in PILOTING User Group (<https://pilotng-project.eu/>) Privacy Notice The actual personal details of the participating members of PILOTING User Group that will be kept by the project are name, surname, affiliation, expertise and email address. These details will be kept for the purposes of PILOTING research and only while kept only throughout the project duration (until 31/12/2023). Any dissemination of these details will be done internally to PILOTING project. Any other usage will be notified to members per case. These data will be stored to the dedicated internal PILOTING server (PILOTING consortium access), while each member will have the right to be removed from this list at any time (with an email to pilotng-project@cattec.aero). With the acceptance in participating to this user-group, each member accepts the above policy in data purpose, duration, access and right to be forgotten (as policies of GDPR).

Figure 3. Invitation email to the “European Robotic & AI projects applied to inspection and maintenance” PILOTING workshops.

NOTE: The templates included in the annexes (Annex I: Participant Information Sheet Template and Annex II: Informed consent form Template) have been elaborated within the WP1 “Ethics requirements”, required in the Post-Grant Requirement document and included in the deliverables D1.1 , D1.2 and D9.1. The same templates are included in the these deliverables because it was explicitly requested in this document (see Figure 4) and are related to the same subject: the protection of the personal data of the humans that participate in the project activities. As you can

see in Annex II: Informed consent form Template, this template includes different types of activities and will be adapted to its use.

The 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with are included as deliverables in this work package.

D1.1 : H - Requirement No. 1 [6]

2.1. The procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants must be included in D8.1 (M6) 2.2. The informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans must be included in D8.1 (M6). 2.3. Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be included in D8.1 (M6)

D1.2 : POPD - Requirement No. 2 [6]

4.1. The applicant must check if a declaration on compliance and/or authorisation is required under national law for collecting and processing personal data as described in the proposal. If yes, the declaration on compliance and/or authorisation must be kept on file. 4.2. If no declaration on compliance or authorisation is required under the applicable national law, a statement from the designated Data Protection Officer that all personal data collection and processing will be carried out according to EU and national legislation must be kept on file. 4.4. Detailed information on the procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction, and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation must be included in D8.1 (M6) 4.6. Detailed information on the informed consent procedures in regard to the collection, storage, and protection of personal data must be must be included in D8.1 (M6) 4.7. Templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be included in D8.1 (M6)

Figure 4. Description of the WP1 deliverables required in the Post-Grant Requirement document.

It is important to clarify that in the above Figure, D8.1 is referring to D9.1. The numbers of the WP were changed from the initial proposal once WP1 was created in order to accommodate the two activities related to the Post-Grant ethics requirements.

➤ **Questions related to the data processing**

11. If personal data are processed, what kind of informed consent procedure will you apply? Please describe it.

In the context of PILOTING project, an informed consent procedure concerning the collection, storage and protection of personal data has been defined and implemented. Before collecting any personal data, the data subject will be informed about what type of information will be collected, what the aim is and how this will be managed. Then, they will be asked to sign an Informed consent form to express their consent. This form has been defined following the legal requirement. The voluntary character of participation will be stated explicitly in the consent form. The Informed consent form includes generic details about the project and offers contacts information. It must also inform the participants on their rights about the collection and the usage of their data. However, as it was commented before, the Information and Informed Consent clauses/terms can be accepted by the subject through a web form (accomplishing the GDPR).

The participants will be assured that their answers will be used only for the purpose of the specific survey.

12. If personal data are processed, what is the purpose of the data processing? What are the expected benefits of the processing?

Information will be processed during the phase of data analysis and will be shown in project reports. It will not be possible to identify the source of the information. The results of this investigation may be published in scientific journals or conferences and may be used in further studies. Benefits are restricted to the contributions of the study on bridges, refineries and tunnels. Results will be shared with participants in order to inform their professional work.

13. If personal data are processed, how long is the personal data kept? What will happen with the personal data afterwards? Please answer both from the perspective of research carried out during the PILOTING project.

If personal data are processed, these will be only for the project and will be preserved for 48 months, the project's life cycle of the work in an anonymised and aggregated way. The recorded data will not include any personal identification; hence it will not be possible to identify you afterwards.

14. If personal data are processed, how do you ensure the security of data? Please describe.

All the personal data collected will be stored according to the EU GDPR regulation, in an internal server related to the project, which is not accessible from non-authorised personnel.

15. If personal data are processed, is the access to the personal data restricted? What are the rules of access (with special attention to its conditions, mode, and limits)?

The personal data collected within the project activities will be confidential and accessible only by authorised personnel. Only the results of the project reports about the feedback obtained from the I&M community will be published, but it will not be possible to identify the source of information.

3.1.2 Questions related to technical aspects

Following the aspects studied in deliverable D91. (Principles for impact assessment of PILOTING against SoEL requirements), the questions related to technical aspects will be oriented to:

1. Data protection
2. Legal aspects related to the operation of Unmanned Vehicles
3. Ethical and legal aspects related to Artificial Intelligence

3.1.2.1 Questions related to data protection

1. What types of data will be collected? Can a natural person be identified with the collected data (in itself or by combination with other data)?

In general, no personal data will be collected. The typical type of data collected in the PILOTING project will be:

- Pictures and videos pointing to the structure being inspected.
- Robotic datasets (video and other sensors).
- Robot position and pose data relative to asset.
- Data referring to the current state of the infrastructure.
- 3D Point clouds.
- Ultrasonic measurement data.
- Asset information (ID, Location, Type)
- Alarms
- Checklists
- Mission related data: mission plan, exclusion areas, inspection notes.

In general, a natural person cannot be identified from the collected data and by any combination with other data. However, some individuals in the area might be filmed by the robot, no natural person will be identified in any way by this data.

On the other hand, users that need access to the IVP and DMS are registered in the DMS. This includes email address, which will serve as the user id. User data to be recorded will typically be user name, company name and contact details. This data can be used to identify a person. Apart from this, DMS will not be collecting any data but will be storing and distributing all the data produced from other modules. This means photos, xmls, pdfs, point clouds etc. The AI system will produce photographs and annotated photographs of damage on wall segments in civil infrastructure as well as xml files with metadata. No natural person will be identified.

2. Will any personal data be collected during the use cases? If so, please describe.

In general, no personal data will be collected. The DMS does not collect but if there is a subscription system it will store the login information of system users (maybe name of the inspector and robot operator, but it could be reduced to the company). Also, it is important to point out that AI services will not collect any personal data.

3. If you feel that your entity does not collect/process personal data in the course of its project activities, please explain.

PILOTING partners are not interested in collecting any personal data in the technical solutions, which are only focused on processing data related to the inspected assets.

PILOTING robotic vehicles only will collect sensors data on-site, which will not involve any personal data. In addition, regarding AI developments, no person recognition is expected to be put in place. The scenarios are going to be restricted and no external personnel is expected to enter the area during the missions. Coincidental images of people will not have any means of relating those to personal data.

However, as it was mentioned in the previous questions, data from users that need access to the IVP and DMS (like name of the inspector and robot operator, company name or contact details) will be stored in the DMS, but these could be reduced to the company.

4. If you process personal data, do you handle special categories of personal data (sensitive data)?

In general, during the PILOTING technical activities, no personal data will be collected. Just login information of system users to access to the IVP and DMS could be collected and stored in the DMS. Furthermore, this type of data could be reduced to the PILOTING I&M platform operator. No sensitive data is expected to be collected.

5. If personal data are processed, does the collected data meet the requirements of relevancy and accuracy? How do you ensure that data will remain accurate when disclosing it to third parties?

In case of personal data will be processed, the information will be kept up to date as relevant for the PILOTING project and securing access to confidential company data. Persons involved will have been duly informed beforehand. Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties.

6. If personal data are processed, can you estimate the amount of processed data and the number of data subjects?

Yes. The number of users of the PILOTING I&M platform portal will be 20-50 persons (approximately) during the project execution.

7. If personal data are processed, what kind of informed consent procedure will you apply? Please describe it.

In case of personal data will be processed, the same procedure as in the project management activities will apply (see section 3.1.2.1, question 11).

8. If personal data are processed, what is the purpose of the data processing? What are the expected benefits of the processing?

Personal data will be solely used to identify users and provide access authorisation to the PILOTING I&M platform portal.

9. If personal data are processed, how long is the personal data kept? What will happen with the personal data afterwards? Please answer both from the perspective of research carried out during the PILOTING project and that of the functionalities of the system itself under normal (future) operating circumstances.

For, as long as the users need to access the PILOTING I&M platform portal (<3 years).

10. If personal data are processed, how do you ensure the security of data? Please describe.

User data will be stored in DMS. These user data will be maintained through the IVP, which has access authorisation and secured communication (https). It is important outlining that all data

stored, including those are not processed, will abide will all the SoTA security considerations fully compliant to GDPR.

11. If personal data are processed, is the access to the personal data restricted? What are the rules of access (with special attention to its conditions, mode, and limits)?

The user data stored in the DMS will be limited to application admin role.

12. Are the processing operations documented? How are the records maintained? What are the rules of access to this documentation?

The operations could be documented in reports that will be recorded in internal servers which will be accessible only for PILOTING partners. However, these reports will not include any personal data. Audit trails of user maintenance activities will not be maintained.

13. How do you demonstrate compliance with data protection law?

Whenever it will be necessary to collect any personal data, informed consent procedures would be followed (see section 3.1.1.1, question 10). Furthermore, within PILOTING project, the best practice security measures are in place. The personal data collected within the project activities will be confidential and accessible only by authorised personnel.

3.1.2.2 Questions related to the operation of Unmanned Vehicles

1. What type of Unmanned Vehicle you plan to operate?

CATEC: 3 different multirotors below 25 kg.

ETHZ: Robotnik UGV.

USE: We will operate rotary-wing aerial vehicles, also known as multicopters, with a maximum take-off mass (MTOW) below 10kg.

WTR: Magnetic crawler operated inside confined space.

SINTEF: SINTEF plan to use the RB-CAR vehicle of Robotnik, see RBNK.

RBNK: Unmanned ground vehicles.

2. Is there any European or National regulation in place that currently applies to the operation of this (these) Unmanned Vehicle(s)?

For Drones and aerial robots, the regulation that applies is the new EASA (European Union Aviation Safety Agency) regulation. Concretely, EU Regulations 2019/947 and 2019/945 set the framework for the safe operation of drones in European skies. These regulations are applicable from December 30, 2020. On the other hand, the Spanish Agency for Aerial Safety (AESA) is in charge of implementing the European regulations, as well as of keeping a registry of all the aerial vehicles and operators in Spain.

For crawlers, the regulation that applies is Machinery directive, EMC directive, ROHS/REACH. Finally, for UGVs (Unmanned Ground Vehicles), there is no direct regulation yet. There are reference standards like ISO 3691-4:2020 Industrial Trucks – Safety requirements and

verification Part 4: Driverless industrial trucks and their systems, which are not applicable in a non-industrial application.

3. Does the Unmanned Vehicle that you plan to operate currently fulfill this regulation?

For aerial vehicles, the prototypes will follow the new European regulation and they will be registered to obtain the necessary permits to flight or authorisations.

For the crawlers to be used in the project, the answer is yes.

In relation with the UGVs, the recommendations on other standards that can serve as references will be followed.

4. If not, is there any aspect of the Unmanned Vehicle that could be an important obstacle to fulfill this regulation in the future?

For aerial vehicles and crawlers, no major obstacle has been identified.

For the UGVs, the absence of specific regulation is actually an obstacle if the robot is not found compliant in the future.

5. Do you envision any other regulation that could apply to the operation of the Unmanned Vehicle (ATEX, environmental, etc.) in PILOTING scenarios?

For all robotic vehicles that may operate in a refinery (aerial, crawler and ground), ATEX regulation is important to be considered.

Specifically for UGVs, as in point 1, the closest is ISO 3691-4:2020 Industrial Trucks – Safety requirements and verification Part 4: Driverless industrial trucks and their systems.

6. If yes, does the Unmanned Vehicle that you plan to operate currently fulfill these other regulations?

ATEX regulation is quite complex to be fulfilled by aerial vehicles since the fact of being flying can generate enough energy to start an ignition process. ATEX was designed for fixed equipment, and we think that ATEX should be adapted for mobile (and even more flying machines) equipment, before applying it to aerial robots.

On the other hand, for PILOTING ground robots, they partially fulfill the mentioned ISO standard.

7. If not, is there any aspect of the Unmanned Vehicle an important obstacle to fulfill these other regulations in the future?

The main concern related with not being able to fulfill ATEX regulation lies on the fact that the risk should be mitigated by specific permits. These mitigations may depend on each specific refinery, and therefore, it can complicate the application of the technology, since in each refinery some specific requirements could be different.

This is especially true for the aerial vehicles. For the ground vehicles, we think fulfilling ATEX regulation is a specific aspect of industrial development after the project. In fact, there are already some UGVs on the market that fulfill this regulation.

8. Do you envision that any of these regulations could affect the operation or the advanced functionalities of these Unmanned Vehicles that you plan to develop within PILOTING project?

No, since autonomous functionalities and project objectives can be fulfilled without fulfilling ATEX regulation.

On the other hand, and in case the ground vehicle will be driving autonomously on a road that is partially open for traffic it may be relevant to consider regulations regarding to testing and operation of autonomous vehicles on roads. As commented above, there is not yet any regulation that covers this case. Then, within PILOTING a driver can be in the vehicle to fulfill regulations.

9. Do you envision that any current regulation (or the lack of it) could affect the future exploitation of the Unmanned Vehicles to be developed within PILOTING project?

First, ATEX regulation may limit the possibilities of autonomy and use cases for aerial robots.

Moreover, it is currently unclear if autonomous agent without human supervision would be allowed in ATEX areas.

With respect to crawlers, safety risks from robot managed by restricting access to operation space (confined space) could affect future exploitation. For example, safety standards that govern robot and human collaboration (like AGVs / AMPs to UL3100).

For UGVs, in the current situation where the regulations are not well defined, or not uniform across jurisdictions the exploitation can be more challenging.

3.1.2.3 Question related to ethical and legal aspects related to Artificial Intelligence

1. Which type of AI algorithms you plan to develop within PILOTING project?

Artificial intelligence algorithms will be developed to automatically detect defects in infrastructures. Also, deep convolutional neuronal networks will be implemented and trained to detect such defects.

2. Do you think that the AI algorithms to be developed in PILOTING could be related to any ethical issue? Please explain in any case.

No. The algorithm will perform post-processing, i.e. detecting and/or classification of material failures. Then, we do not think that the algorithms can have any ethical issue.

3. Do you think that the AI algorithms to be developed in PILOTING fulfill the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (published by EC in April 2019)?

Yes, we believe that the algorithms will fulfill the ethical guidelines.

4. Do you think that the AI algorithms to be developed in PILOTING follow the Policy and Investment Recommendations for Trustworthy AI (published in June 2019)?

Yes, we believe that the AI algorithms will follow the Policy and Investment Recommendations for Trustworthy AI.

5. Is there standard or regulation (related to I&M) that PILOTING AI algorithms should fulfill?

PILOTING partners are not aware of it. Then, we think that there are not any additional regulations that must be followed.

6. Do the AI algorithms that you plan to operate currently fulfill this regulation?

Not applicable since we are not aware of any additional regulation.

7. If not, is there any aspect of the AI algorithms that could be an important obstacle to fulfill this regulation in the future?

We do not believe that there is any aspect that is an obstacle to fulfill the regulation in the future.

8. Do you envision that any of these regulations could affect the operation of these AI algorithms that you plan to develop within PILOTING project?

The only aspect that can affect the operation of these algorithms it is the fact that it is common that inspection data should be validated by a certified inspector. In PILOTING, the AI algorithms will be used to facilitate the work to eh inspector, but we do not know yet if the asset owners will impose any additional requirement on the AI algorithms to be used as a validated tool for certified inspectors.

9. Do you envision that any current regulation (or the lack of it) could affect the future exploitation of the AI algorithms to be developed within PILOTING project?

Apart from the above comment, we do not envision that any current regulation could affect the future exploitation of PILOTING AI algorithms.

3.2 SoEL IMPACT ASSESSMENT ANALYSIS

Once the possible risks of non-compliance with the SoEL requirements have been identified, these will be analysed.

For PILOTING project, a risk is defined as an event, which could potentially have an adverse effect on a team's progress and success. Any risk has a severity of the impact (or consequences) and a probability (or likelihood) of occurrence. The quantification and qualification of risk is based in these two dimensions. In order to have a proper analysis of the risk and of course to be able to prioritise when it comes to the planning of responses both probability and impact of a risk needs to be defined.

Risk **probability**, or likelihood, is the possibility of a risk event occurring. Probability of risk to occur can be mapped to one of the following three-grade scale:

- Low- In similar activities, few or no occurrences of the risk happened, thus risk can be handled reliably. Risk shall be periodically monitored and high-level action plan in case risk occurs should be elaborated upon. Depending on the nature or root cause, a set of preventative or mitigation actions should be identified.

- Medium - Risks of similar nature have happened rarely in other similar activities and the current situation has few assumptions that are somewhat favourable to the emergence of the risk. A detailed action plan should be developed in case of the event occur. Depending on the nature or root cause, set of avoidance or mitigation actions should be assessed and broken down into steps.
- High- There is a significantly high chance that the risk will occur. Major trade-offs between SoEL requirements and PILOTING functionalities should be thoroughly discussed and a set of avoidance or mitigation actions (depending on the nature or root cause) should be ready for implementation.

Impacts are often defined as the consequences, or effects of a risk event on the project objectives. A five-grade scale is detailed as follows:

- Low- If the risk occurs, it does not threaten the rights and freedoms of the individual, or causes necessity of only minor or no modification or adaptation of the project. Limitation of the SoEL requirements remains lawful, necessary, and proportionate.
- Medium- If the risk occurs, it can be deemed as a threat to the rights and freedoms of the individual. Several elements in the system should be revised and/or modified (however staying on an acceptable level).
- High- If the risk occurs, rights and freedoms of the individual are highly affected, thus one or more goals of the project will not be met. Significant revision and re-orientation (e.g. technical) is needed.

The risk rating is the overall effect of a risk happening. For PILOTING, risk ratings of Low, Medium, or High are assigned based on the following risk matrix:

Probability/Impact	Low	Medium	High
High	Medium	High	High
Medium	Low	Medium	High
Low	Low	Low	Medium

Table 7. Risk matrix

These categories can help the consortium prioritise between risks and decide which risks should be mitigated or avoided first and which should leave space for other treatment options. The answers provided to the questionnaire contain information to identify, assess, and categorise the probability and impact of risks against SoEL requirements. For PILOTING, risk ratings of Low, Medium, or High imply:

- Low, if Very Unlikely or Unlikely to occur,
- Medium, if Possible to occur,
- High, if Likely or Almost Certain to occur.

Table 8 and Table 9 show the analysis of the risks identified on the PILOTING SoEL Impact Assessment.

3.3 SoEL IMPACT ASSESSMENT EVALUATION AND TREATMENT

After the project's risks have been identified and assessed, the approach to handle each significant risk must be developed. There are essentially four techniques or options for handling risks:

- **Avoid:** when you avoid the risk, it means you change your plan to completely eliminate the probability of the risk, or the effect of the risk, if it does occur.
- **Transfer:** risk transference occurs when the negative impact is shifted to a third party, such as through an insurance policy or penalty clause in a contract. The risk may still occur however the financial impact will be somewhat displaced. Risk transference usually involves some type of contractual agreement.
- **Mitigate:** risk mitigation occurs when you proactively change the plan to minimise the impact or probability of the risk occurring. Risk mitigation does not eliminate the risk and as such there will be some residual risk remaining.
- **Accept:** there are few risks which are out of control of project organisation and project manager has no other option but to accept them and still continue running the project by finding alternate ways to tackle the issues arising from these risks. For all identified risks, the various handling techniques should be evaluated in terms of feasibility, expected effectiveness, cost and schedule implications, the effect on the system's technical quality/performance and the most suitable technique selected.

The following tables will describe the identified risks, the significance of the risk and the contingency plan defined.

Table 8. Management identified risks

Risk N°	Description	Probability	Impact	Risk response	Contingency Plan
1	Missing or inadequate legal requirements of GDPR for data processing during the project's life cycle	Low	High	MITIGATE	Informed consent procedures have been defined and implemented. Only authorised personnel will have access to the data collected in project management activities. If sensitive data are collected, these will be preserved in an anonymised and aggregated way and deleted after the project end. Finally, PILOTING project has appointed a Data Project Officer (Inmaculada Huertas Olivares) who can answer any question regarding the GDPR fulfilment.
2	Missing or inadequate legal requirements	Medium	High	TRANSFER/ MITIGATE	The information obtained from project management activities like surveys/workshops will be used to make project reports / analyse the

	of GDPR for data processing after the project's life cycle				<p>feedback from the I&M community or make publications in scientific journals. These results do not make it possible to identify the source of information.</p> <p>About the recorded data, only authorised personnel will be able the access and these will be deleted after the end of the project.</p> <p>Once the project has been completed, the data controller will continue to be responsible for treating this risk.</p> <p>Finally, PILOTING project has appointed a Data Project Officer (Inmaculada Huertas Olivares) who can answer any question regarding the GDPR fulfilment.</p>
3	Inefficient communication channels to obtain SoEL feedback from stakeholders	Low	Medium	MITIGATE	<p>Four different channels have been established to obtain stakeholder's feedback. In case of an inadequate communication with the stakeholders through these channels, PILOTING project has made available the following email to send any request or complaint: piloting-project@catec.aero.</p>
4	Insufficient information for data subjects	Medium	High	MITIGATE	<p>PILOTING project provides a specific email (piloting-project@catec.aero) to solve any concerns related to personal data recruitment and treatment.</p>
5	Insufficient security for personal data maintenance and storage	Low	High	AVOID (measures already taken)	<p>As it was described in the D1.2, POPD - Requirement N°2, personal data will be recorded in the internal server during the cycle life of the project. Only authorised personnel will be access to this information.</p>
6	Withdrawal of a partner and lose control of the previous data collected	Low	High	TRANSFER	<p>This situation is regulated on the basis of the PILOTING consortium's Grant Agreement.</p>

Table 9. Technical identified risks

Risk N°	Description	Probability	Impact	Risk response	Contingency Plan
Data protection					

7	Incidental personal data collection during the use cases	Low	High	MITIGATE	The risk of collecting incidental personal data from 3rd parties has been minimised. However, during the use cases, there are possibilities that natural persons can be captured on video/image, although there is no intention to identify persons from the data. In this case, the image collected will be modified or deleted so that the person cannot be identified. If this is not possible, the defined informed consent procedures (see section 3.1.1.1, question 7) will be followed.
8	Sensitive data is processed. Sensors might capture sensitive data.	Low	High	AVOID (measures already taken)	The system has been designed to not collect any data that would be considered sensitive personal data.
9	Missing or inadequate legal requirements of GDPR for data processing during the project's life cycle	Low	High	MITIGATE	See Table 8, Risk 1.
10	Missing or inadequate legal requirements of GDPR for data processing after the project's life cycle	Medium	High	TRANSFER/ MITIGATE	See Table 8, Risk 2.
11	Insufficient information for data subjects	Medium	High	MITIGATE	See Table 8, Risk 4.
12	Insufficient security for personal data maintenance and storage	Low	High	AVOID (measures already taken)	See Table 8, Risk 5.
Operation of Unmanned Vehicles					
13	ATEX certification for UAVs	Medium	Medium	AVOID	The current use cases with UAVs are oriented to areas of the refinery where ATEX

					certification is not required. Also, PILOTING partners are working to work on the development of operational mitigations that may be useful to operate non-ATEX UAVs in ATEX zones in the future.
14	Certification of UGVs	Medium	High	AVOID	The use cases involve the use of UGVs in areas that are not open to regular traffic in open and public roads. This fact can facilitate the use of UGVs in the future.
15	Safety risks standards affecting crawler design and operation	Medium	High	MITIGATE	Latest safety standards related to robotics vehicles are taken into consideration in the design and development of the crawler system and operational concept.
Artificial Intelligence					
16	Regulation related to AI algorithms is mandatory in the future	Medium	Low	AVOID	AI algorithms in PILOTING are related to the detection of defects in infrastructure, so they are not targeting any sensible issue related to privacy or ethics. Anyway, during PILOTING project, new developments on a future AI regulation will be closely monitored
17	AI algorithms applied to inspection are required to be certified	Medium	Medium	AVOID	AI algorithms results are always validated by an experience inspector. In the future, and after the AI algorithms are validated for an extensive period of time, if the system is planned to be used without any supervision, it is expected that some type

					of certification will be required.
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4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable integrates the results of the impact assessment against the different SoEL requirements defined in the D9.1 “Principles for impact assessment of PILOTING against SoEL requirements” and also recommendations on how to improve PILOTINGs developments on these topics.

All the partners have made a valuable contribution making its best effort to evaluate its activities in the PILOTING framework against the PILOTING SoEL requirements. This deliverable is considered a living document which will be updated and further completed during the second development cycle of the project (M36).

As mentioned above, the aim of this report is to ensure that any element of PILOTING and its foreseen applications are in line with the SoEL requirements in order to promote the long-term exploitation of PILOTING system. To this end, this deliverable:

- Makes an overview of the project business projection, in order to take in account the SoEL requirements of the final solution to be exploited after the project concludes.
- Completes a 1st impact assessment against the Guidelines defined in the deliverable D9.1. This 1st report is more focused on the technologies developed within the project. In the next report, deliverable D9.4, when the project will be more advanced and the solutions more clearly defined, the impact assessment will also take into account the business projections.

After the SoEL impact assessment has been finalized, the following recommendations for the PILOTING developments have been identified:

- Even though ATEX certification is out of scope of PILOTING, and even for some of the robotic vehicles, such as aerial robots, it is almost impossible to obtain due to the strict restrictions of the current ATEX certification, this could be a stopper for the future exploitation at scale of PILOTING technologies at refineries. Then, the approach use in PILOTING is the application of operational mitigations to ensure safety. This is why it has been concluded that it will be very beneficial to work towards a standardization of the operational mitigations that could be accepted from the major Oil&Gas companies. So, the same solution could be used at different refineries and will avoid the risk that each refinery will consider different requirements for the operational mitigations, and therefore, different requirements on the robotic vehicles obstructing the future exploitation at scale of the developed technologies. This is a long-term goal, but at least, within PILOTING project we should work on best practices that could be used as the baseline for a future standard in relation with the operation of robots in refineries, without ATEX, but with certain operational

mitigations implemented. These best practices should be refined after the first pilot experiments and validated during the second round of pilot experiments.

- The lack of regulation for UGVs, crawlers and indoor UAVs (tunnel scenario) could be seen as a first stage as an advantage since there is no initial restriction or extra requirements to be fulfilled by the robot manufacturers. However, it also involves a risk in the way that if in a future regulation is established imposing new requirements that are not fulfilled by the initial design, a major redesign and upgrade of the robotic vehicles will be needed (usually involving a high investment from the robot manufacturer to being able to continue in the European market). This is why it is important to continue monitoring any progress of the regulation in these three cases (UGV, crawlers and indoor UAVs) in Europe, and also worldwide that could help to get ahead of any future regulation.
- In relation to the above recommendation, it has been decided to follow the European UAV regulation even for the design and development of the indoor UAV. This is a conservative approach since it is not mandatory to follow this regulation for indoor UAVs. However, it will allow ensuring that the developed solution for the indoor UAV is well-accepted for any future client since we do not expect that the HSE (Health and Safety Environment) requirements will be stricter than the European UAV regulation ones.
- Since AI-regulation is currently being generated and this has been pointed out as a major topic for the European Commission in order to be sure to develop ethical AI solutions, it is important to continuously monitor the progress in this regulation and continuously ensure that PILOTING developments are aligned with the new regulations that will be generated in the next years. This is especially important in case it is finally needed by the European Commission to “certify” in a certain way the ethical dimension of the AI-algorithms.
- It is also important to incorporate in the sensor systems, on-board the robotic vehicles, functionalities that will ensure that no personal data is transmitted to the PILOTING I&M platform, so it will be easier to demonstrate that the PILOTING inspection system fulfils with GDPR. For example, it has been identified the possibility to incorporate a post-processing SW that will automatically detect persons in the images, and if this is case, it will automatically delete these pictures. These new identified requirements, after the SoEL impact assessment, will be incorporated in the PILOTING developments during the second development iteration planned after the first pilot experiments.

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Annex I: Participant Information Sheet Template

H2020-ICT-2018-2020

European Commission

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Project Acronym	PILOTING
Project Name	PILOTS for robotic and Inspection and maintenance Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and prototype applications
Grant Agreement n°	871542
Start date of the project	01/01/2020
End date of the project	31/12/2023
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871542	

CONTACT DETAILS:

DATE:

INTRODUCTION

You have been invited to take in the PILOTING research and innovation project. Before making a decision on whether you want to participate or not, please read this document carefully. Please ask all the questions you may have so you can be completely sure to understand all the proceedings of the study, including risks and benefits. Take time to decide whether or not to take part.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Current European refineries and civil infrastructures, like tunnels and bridges, are ageing, and therefore gradually become deteriorated, especially taking into consideration the current and future economic situation in Europe where large investments in renewing infrastructures are not foreseen.

Then, it is paramount important to increase the efficiency and quality of inspection and maintenance activities in order to keep the necessary safety levels in these ageing infrastructures. To overcome this important challenge, PILOTING proposes the adaptation, integration, and demonstration of robotic solutions, in an integrated platform, which will be tested and evaluated in three large-scale pilots: refineries (Oil&Gas sector), bridges/viaducts

H2020-ICT-2018-2020

and tunnels (Civil/Transport Infrastructure sector) with the involvement of all the actors that conform the full value chain.

PILOTING CONSORTIUM

PILOTING started in January 2020 and will finish in December 2023. The PILOTING consortium is composed of 14 partners. The overall action coordinator is Dr. Antidio Viguria, CTO of the Avionics and Systems Division of Andalusian Foundation for Aerospace Development (FADA-CATEC) and the PILOTING partners, which include the following:

- Andalusian Foundation for Aerospace Development **Spain**
- Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich **Switzerland**
- University of Seville **Spain**
- Chevron Oronite **France**
- Ferrovial Agroman S.A **Spain**
- Honeywell International s.r.o. **Czech Republic**
- GE Inspection Robotics **Switzerland**
- Applus Rvis **Netherlands**
- Egnatia ODOS AE **Greece**
- Quasset B.V **Netherlands**
- SINTEF AS **Norway**
- INLECOM **Greece**
- Institute of Communication and Computer Systems **Greece**
- Robotnik Automation **Spain**

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

Participation in the study is voluntary. You can withdraw your consent to participate in the study at any time and without stating any particular reason. This will not have any consequences for your further treatment. If you wish to participate will be able to keep a copy of this information sheet and you should indicate your agreement to the online consent form. If you agree to participate at this time, you may later on withdraw your consent without your treatment being affected in any way.

PRIVACY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

Responses you give in the questionnaires, workshop and focus group will be recorded.

Your recorded data will not include any personal identification; hence it will not be possible to identify you afterwards.

Information will be processed during the phase of data analysis and will be shown in project reports. It will not be possible to identify the source of the information. The results of this investigation may be published in scientific journals or conferences and may be used in further studies. Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties.

H2020-ICT-2018-2020

The authorization for the use and access to this information is valid until the end of the study unless you decide to cancel it before. If you should decide to deny your consent, please contact the leading investigator and let her/him know of your intention of leaving the study.

Your decision to whether or not give your authorization for the use and diffusion of the information provided by you is completely voluntary. However, if you do not provide the investigators with this authorization now or if you cancel it in the future, you will not be able to participate in this study.

ARE THERE RISKS OR BENEFITS IF I PARTICIPATE?

Participating in the project is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress will be the same as any experienced in everyday life.

No risks are foreseen in relation to participation since privacy and confidentiality are granted.

Benefits are restricted to the contributions of the study on bridges, refineries and tunnels being attacked by all types of extreme physical, natural and man-made incidents, and cyber-attacks, the PILOTING consortium, and transport operators in Greece, Spain and France, who aim to improve the quality of transportations in case of natural or man-made extreme events.

Results will be shared with participants in order to inform their professional work.

QUESTIONS/CONCERNS

If you have any further questions or want clarification regarding this research and/or your participation, please contact:

Annex II: Informed consent form Template

H2020-ICT-2018-2020

European Commission

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Project Acronym	PILOTING
Project Name	PILOts for robotic and Inspection and maintenance Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and prototype applications
Grant Agreement n°	871542
Start date of the project	01/01/2020
End date of the project	31/12/2023
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871542	

CONTACT DETAILS:

DATE:

WHAT WILL I BE ASKED TO DO?

You will be asked to participate in answer a questionnaire or join a workshop to support the development of the project with your valuable feedback offering.

The questionnaire isn't expected to take a considerable amount of time to be filled. You are under no pressure to answer it. You are free not to answer to questions on topics that you do not wish. All the necessary precautions will be taken to protect your anonymity and confidentiality. If you wish to stop the process, the questionnaire will be destroyed if you do not wish of us to keep it as is.

The workshop is intended to chronologically comply with the agenda schedule. Participation is voluntary. You are under no pressure to participate if you don't wish. You are free not to occupy yourself on matters that you do not wish. All the necessary precautions will be taken to protect your anonymity and confidentiality. If you wish to withdraw from the workshop, any information collected to that point will be destroyed if you do not wish of us to use them.

TYPE OF INFORMATION THAT WILL BE COLLECTED

The personal data that will be collected during this activity, include name, surname, email address and work position.

Even with you permission we will not refer to you or quote you in any publication without allowing you to verify the accuracy of quotes that are being used. Information collected will

H2020-ICT-2018-2020

be relevant only to your official role such as length of time in this position, responsibilities and prior relevant experience.

Please put a check mark on the line corresponding to your willingness to be identified:

You may quote me and use my name: Yes ___ No ___

CAN WE CONTACT YOU FOR FURTHER RESEARCH?

You may contact me in the future for further research related to the PILOTING project:

Yes ___ No ___

CONFIRMATION

Your participation in this study is only possible if you freely and independently sign this consent to authorize us to use the data you provide. If you do not wish to do so, please do not participate in this study.

Your signature on this form indicates that you:

- Are 18 years or older and am competent to provide consent
- Have read and understood the information about the project, as provided in the PILOTING Information Sheet.
- Voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- Understand that even if you agree to participate now, you can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
- Understand that all information you provide will be treated confidentially.
- Understand that in any report on the results of this research your identity will remain anonymous
- Understand that if you inform the researcher that you or someone else is at risk of harm they may have to report this to the relevant authorities - they will discuss this with you first but may be required to report with or without your permission.
- Understand that signed consent forms will be retained until the end of the project
- Understand that under freedom of information legalization you are entitled to access the information you have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
- Understand that you are free to contact any of the people involved in the research, through the contact details provided in the bottom of the form, to seek further clarification and information.

H2020-ICT-2018-2020

Participant's name:

Participant's Signature:

Date:

Researcher's Name:

Researcher's Signature:

Date:

QUESTION/CONCERNS

If you have any further questions or want clarification regarding this research and/or your participation, please contact

Thank you for your collaboration!